

Destination Digital: Defining the Potential and Prospect of Digital Game-Based and E-Learning

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Digital Game-Based

Learning is an innovative tool to breathe fun and enthusiasm into learning. Where previous generations of kids preferred to play with action figures and miniature vehicles, a casual visit to any major department store will prove that touch-sensitive tablet PCs and smartphones, along with the latest gaming consoles and networking gear, have transformed the dynamics of contemporary consumers' growth and development (Makris, 2006; Toys R Us, 2008). Studies suggest the "fun" variable tips the balance in favor of Digital Game-Based Learning's efficacy and popularity (Hwang, Sung, Hung, Huang, Tsai, 2012).

Hence, the objective of this article was to explore the potential of video and computer games as E-Learning or gamification to enhance educational outcomes and offer solutions for a sustainable future (Rao, 2011).

Undoubtedly, within the past 30 years, human beings have flocked with increasing zeal around the billion-dollar gaming industry in search of an innocuous, yet exciting activity, to replace tedious tasks: rote memorization and routines are laborious.

Optimally, education should be as exciting and gripping as a modern, immersive 3D video or computer game (Deubel, 2006). Rondon, Sassi & Furquim (2013), demonstrated that DGBL offers at least as much

knowledge retention as traditional methods (lectures, presentations).

Therefore, the rationale for this article resulted from the trend in society and culture toward a need for innovative learning strategies as the human population continues to grow and traditional resources and facilities become both obsolete and strained (Rao, 2011). Furthermore, the fun potential of games represents a logistical and economic loophole exploitable for efficient, cost-effective, and convenient learning strategies.

In other words, the best way to make individuals learn is by making the learning intuitively fun and engaging, enabling the dissolution of artificial barriers between education, leisure, school, and home (Deubel, 2006; Rao, 2011; Rondon, Sassi & Furquim de Andrade, 2013).

Moreover, the described potential of DGBL to transform the educational experience into an absorbing and compelling adventure offers a unique intervention to enhance the quality of life in developing countries, where students faced with stress and hardship often lack the patience, discipline, and resource to commit solely to traditional tools as lectures, books, and notes. Deficits in economic and

physical infrastructures in developing countries, distinctively in remote rural areas, further emphasized the pivotal and unique role E-Learning in general, and DGBL, specifically, assumed to realize an effective and accredited education (Khan & Williams, 2010).

The instantiation of E-Learning and digital game-based learning has gained ground through students' increased use of consumer electronics to improve their quality of life in all areas and ventures. For instance,

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Deubel (2006) identified multiple educational benefits unique to digital game-based learning. The sense of enjoyment students derive from such media contributes

to an innately formative and self-sufficient learning experience. Thus, Deubel (2006), along with numerous related studies, shed light on the research question, "How can DGBL transform education into a fun and dynamic learning experience?"

Tsa, Yu & Hsiao (2012) continued to address this iconic question through an experiment with the motorcycle racing game "Super Delivery." This teaches electronics terms and measurements.

The game captivated students during the experiment; students expressed a desire to take the game home to continue playing it. This game immersed students in its gameplay to the extent that they tended to ignore learning the terms, which indicated a need to interweave the educational elements more intelligently with the gameplay design. This study was remarkable in that it proved that playing motivation is negatively correlated with learning motivation. Since students were so compelled by the game itself, they ignored the task of learning about electrical terms and procedures. They were more concerned with completing the game and scoring high.

As a result, the researchers concluded that DGBL can become counterproductive when students lack a traditional learning component. They suggest that DGBL would realize its effectiveness through a blended or hybrid learning situation, where the concepts taught in the game were reinforcements to the subject matter taught by an instructor in a class.

Further studies, as Hwang, Sung, Hung, Huang & Tsai (2012) pointed out that the learning motivation problem could be alleviated through customizable games responsive to specific students' learning styles. This study, similarly, set up an experimental and control group: the former administering a game to students with different learning styles, the other administering the same game without the learning style augmentation.

The results indicated enhanced

outcomes based on the learning styles. The studies proved that DGBL had the potential to inspire independent and self-directed learning, sizing up to traditional learning and even exhibiting the potential to outperform.

The first research question regarding the transformational potential of digital games segued into the second research question that probed to what extent the cognitive stimulation latent and manifest in digital games could convert and bring relief to the educational crisis in war-torn developing countries, as Iraq, Sudan, Syria, Ukraine, and Yemen. The second research question then gave impetus to the credibility and future of E-Learning programs. Certainly, human beings as users do not just want to know the information but also desire to use the information to grow and develop as meaningful contributors to a global economy.

Velloso de Santisteban (2005) surveyed the status of education in war-torn Iraq, noting that 15 years prior to international sanctions and then the war to force regime change, Iraq's educational system served as a role model to the Arab world. The enrollment rate was 100% at compulsory public schools; the literacy rate was 80%, and Iraq's universities exhibited world-class scientists and researchers. The economic sanctions by the United Nations and the large-scale termination of Baathist teachers devastated the

educational system. For instance, the exemplary literacy rate of 85% among women in 1985 declined to merely 45% in 1995 after the sanctions were imposed (Velloso de Santisteban, 2005). Significant deficiencies and setbacks have plagued Iraq across its various administrative support systems, ranging from crippled healthcare, deteriorating streets, and escalation in violence, to a lack of electricity and clean, running water.

Provided that infrastructure improvements would allow at least the operation of portable PCs, the prospect of Digital Game-based Learning and gamification strategies hold a key to safe, accessible educational opportunities. Expansion of current wireless Internet networks to cover developing countries across the globe could offer a provisional solution to the widespread inaccessibility of schools in war-afflicted

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countries (Iraq, Afghanistan, Syria, Yemen, Ukraine, and others).

Kamssu (2005) and Prasad (2010) envision the possibility of a

global wireless network, which lends itself as a resource to counteract fundamentalism and spawn economic opportunities. Prasad (2010) observed that emerging economies serve as a breeding ground even for innovative technologies, which then inspire ecological change globally.

Krueger & Maleckova (2003) confirm that terrorism in developing countries exhibits a complex, multi-faceted origin rooted in education, a lack of decent political conditions, and long-standing feelings of indignity and frustration” (p. 119). The authors of the study found that most terrorists are people with education and professions, yet who have studied alongside religious fundamentalist principles and with a lack of global political awareness.

Ihedioha (2009) observed, as well, that parents in war-torn regions feel uncomfortable sending their children to brick-and-mortar schools due to widespread kidnapping, exposure to bombs and shrapnel, as well as deteriorating school standards. Rao (2011) and Khan & Williams (2010) devoted studies entirely to the status of E-Learning as a global phenomenon, emphasizing that its current pace would soon outstrip traditional forms of education and offer solutions regardless of physical or regional location.

Game-Based learning enables a detachment from regular attendance and exposure to unsafe commuting and participation. The described motivational fun-potential of games enables frustrated students to immerse themselves in a different world focused on a safe exploration of learning, customizable development, and global interactivity (Schneider, 2005).

The third research question in this overview of DGBL proceeded as follows: *how can global leaders develop and establish E-Learning for a sustainable future?* The notable figures in Hellwig's 2013 interview regard the future of E-Learning as an inevitable development that optimally would restore an equitable price/value ratio to ed-

ucation.

Wikipedia's Jimmy Wales observed that informal education has also shifted from libraries and subject experts to publicly accessible online resources. The online learning summit (2013), a conference featuring such leaders as presidents of MIT and Harvard and focused on the future of online and residential education, echoed the remarks in the interviews.

Among the most critical issues was the role of technology in online and residential learning, the extent to which successful online learning can be measured, and the significance of massive open online courses (MOOCs). Current leadership observed a lack of data-gathering and measurability concerning MOOCs. These courses and delivery methods also require integration with accredited models of education to enhance outcomes and yield measurable results.

Undoubtedly, the panelists emphasized that the adoption of online learning methods, as MOOCs, will transform traditional methods of education and their curricula. Conference members overwhelmingly

acknowledged that E-Learning would entail substantial changes to the format, perspective, and identity of higher education. Among the different models that could manifest themselves are ticket-oriented education that offers a transfer process toward a particular goal or toward a global orientation and a problem-oriented education intensively focused on optimally using human

resources and traditional class-time to think about and hopefully also solve conflicts and deficiencies.

For instance, Sal Khan from the YouTube-based Khan Academy, a provider of MOOCs, stresses that online education and E-Learning could deflate the tedium and formality of classroom education, enabling stakeholders to address higher-order learning objectives: diagnostics, assessments, interactive discussion, and problem-solving. Throughout the summit, the participants reiterated that recent technologies require conscientious and deliberate integration alongside humanistic principles, measurable results, adequate funding, and sufficient time for faculty and students to adjust and make use of the technologies.

Khan's leadership innovates upon face-to-face or online classroom time by deferring “lower-order” learning to MOOCs that featured videos and tutorials, and elaborates

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upon the debate between acquiring knowledge vs. effectively using knowledge. The 2012 study on the game “Super Deliver,” as an example, high-

lighted similar concerns that digital games are optimal in conjunction with interactive classrooms or conferences where the knowledge that is transmitted is taken to the next level of discussion and integration. Khan cited research that the human mind is least engaged during lectures and note-taking and the most engaged in challenging situations.

Consequently, DGBL could be used to replace passive lectures and note-taking tasks to transmit fundamental knowledge on a topic in a manner more stimulating to the mind, which would then translate into a more productive, innovative, and resourceful time at a conference or class. In this respect, DGBL would hold a key to time, space, and outcome efficiency and optimization.

One of the few extant studies that specifically measured and explored the feasibility of DGBL in developing countries, Serenelli, Ruggeri & Mangiatordi (2012) conducted an experimental study on primary school children in Montevideo, Uruguay (N=226) in response to an initiative spearheaded by MIT to distribute millions of laptops to developing countries. The study consisted of two experimental groups and one control group. The first experimental group studied a digital tutorial called “Step-by-step Multimedia” in a self-directed learning setting; the kids of the second group individually played an interactive “Learning Game.” A virtual tutor guided both. The control group consisted of a frontal lesson accompanied by slides.

The results of the study indicated that the two media-enriched groups outperformed the control group in test scores administered after one week of students' exposure to the various learning groups. The researchers assessed students' learning outcomes according to a retention test, comprehension test, problem-solving test, and delayed problem-solving test. The students in the experimental group scored higher on the comprehension tests by 20%, and specifically, the DGBL group scored 17% higher on the delayed problem-solving test than the control group.

The authors of the study indicated that these favorable outcomes configure DGBL and E-Learning in general as legitimate means to tackle the three-fold education challenge in developing countries: the differences in the learning of the new generations (commonly called “digital natives”), the increasing educational gaps between rich and poor countries, and the worldwide crisis of economic systems. The authors observed the elevated level of engagement and advantages over traditional education would yield a feasible approach to address these existential and formative challenges, echoing the statements made by the members of the online learning summit. The arguments and examples in this article sought to identify the unique qualities of DGBL: its potential for fun, excitement, and interactive learning, and its concomitant role in the transformation of learning in developing countries.

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